

Restaurant Service Quality: A Literature Study of SERVQUAL Dimensions

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the differences in service quality in various types of restaurants, the impact of employee training on service quality, and the influence of local culture in shaping customer expectations and satisfaction. The literature review revealed that franchise restaurants tend to have higher service consistency due to strict operational standards, while local restaurants emphasize personal service and empathy. Employee training has been shown to improve staff competence, responsiveness, and job satisfaction, which contributes to improving service quality. In addition, local culture plays an important role in shaping customer expectations and strengthening communication relationships between customers and staff through respect for customs, traditions, and the use of culturally appropriate language. Food safety aspects are also a crucial factor in building customer trust, especially in the post-COVID-19 pandemic era. The findings of this study provide practical implications for restaurant managers in optimizing service strategies through HR training and cultural adjustments to improve customer satisfaction and loyalty.

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KEYWORDS: reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism and the food industry have experienced rapid development in the last decade. The restaurant sector as part of the tourism industry plays an important role in shaping the image of tourist destinations as well as supporting the local economy. In this context, service quality is a crucial element that determines customer satisfaction and loyalty. According to Parasuraman et al. (1988), service quality is influenced by five main dimensions, namely tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, which are then known as the SERVQUAL model. This model has been widely used to measure and evaluate service quality in various contexts, including in the restaurant sector.

Research in various countries shows that high service quality can increase customer satisfaction, which ultimately affects repurchase intentions and consumer loyalty (Ryu & Han, 2010; Qin & Prybutok, 2009). In addition, the quality of service in restaurants is also influenced by the service culture and consumer expectations that vary in each region. A study by Elmadağ et al. (2019) tends to highly value the friendliness and politeness of waiters and pay attention to the speed and accuracy of service. This shows that restaurant managers need to understand the local context in developing service strategies.

In a competitive perspective, service quality also plays a major role as a differentiator amidst the proliferation of

restaurants offering similar products. According to Kim et al. (2009) customers tend to prefer restaurants that provide the best service experience even though the price is higher, compared to cheap restaurants but with poor service.

Changes in consumer behavior after the COVID-19 pandemic have also affected the dimensions of service quality. A study by Luo & Xu (2021) shows that aspects of cleanliness and safety have become new dimensions that are taken into account by restaurant customers. Adapting standard health protocols into restaurant services is an important factor in maintaining consumer trust, in addition to the five traditional SERVQUAL dimensions.

Overall, the literature review shows that restaurant service quality is the result of a complex interaction between operational dimensions, local culture, consumer expectations, and global trends. Therefore, further research is needed to identify specific factors that influence customer perceptions of service quality across restaurant segments in. This study aims to provide a deeper understanding of relevant and applicable service improvement strategies in the local context.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Occupational Health and Safety Concept

Tangibles or physical evidence is a SERVQUAL dimension that includes the appearance of facilities,

equipment, personnel, and communication materials (Parasuraman et al., 1988). In the restaurant industry, this includes interior design, cleanliness of the dining room, menu displays, and employee uniforms. A study by Ryu & Han (2023) confirmed that a clean and attractive physical restaurant environment significantly affects perceived quality and customer satisfaction. Wall & Berry (2007) revealed that an aesthetic and neat visual appearance of a restaurant is a major differentiating factor that encourages customers to recommend a restaurant to others who are sensitive to aesthetics and social media image.

Reliability

Reliability Refers to the restaurant's ability to provide promised services accurately and consistently. This dimension includes order accuracy, appropriate serving time, and taste consistency. Kim et al. (2009) found that errors in serving orders were the main cause of customer complaints. Conversely, restaurants that are able to maintain menu consistency and service time show higher levels of satisfaction. Namkung & Jang (2007). also shows that reliability is a key factor in creating long-term customer loyalty in the food service sector.

Responsiveness

Responsiveness describes the willingness of restaurant staff to help customers and provide prompt service. Liu & Lee (2021) showed that the speed of response of waiters in fulfilling customer requests, such as placing the wrong food or adding drinks, greatly affects the overall dining experience. This is in line with the findings of Qin & Prybutok (2009) who highlighted the importance of speed of service in the post-pandemic context, where customers value efficient service to minimize time spent in public spaces.

Assurance

Assurance includes the knowledge and attitude of staff in providing a sense of trust and confidence to customers, including competence, politeness, and the ability to explain products. According to Qin and Prybutok (2009), this dimension becomes increasingly important in restaurants that offer complex or unique menus, where customers require additional explanations. A study by Elmadağ et al. (2019) found that training restaurant staff in communication ethics and product knowledge improved customers' perceptions of professionalism and the safety of the food consumed.

Empathy

Empathy emphasizes personal attention and understanding of customers' individual needs. In the restaurant sector, empathy is reflected in the way staff treat customers, attention to special preferences, and the ability to build emotional connections (Qin & Prybutok, 2009). A study by Nguyen et al. (2018) showed that customers feel valued when restaurant staff remember their preferences or

show concern, such as asking about the spiciness of the food. Empathy-based service is considered to be able to increase customer emotional satisfaction, which leads to high revisit intentions. Overall, the five dimensions of SERVQUAL provide a strong framework for assessing and improving restaurant service quality. Previous literature suggests that each dimension plays a different role depending on market segment, restaurant type, and socio-cultural conditions. In the context of increasingly fierce competition and rising customer expectations post-pandemic, restaurants need to strategically strengthen all these dimensions in a balanced manner.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach with a literature review method to analyze the concept and empirical findings related to restaurant service quality, based on the five dimensions of SERVQUAL: Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy as developed by Parasuraman et al. (1988). The literature review was conducted systematically to collect, summarize, and synthesize relevant previous research findings.

The data sources in this study were obtained from various scientific articles that have been published in accredited national journals and reputable international journals indexed in Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Inclusion criteria include articles discussing service dimensions in the context of the restaurant industry. Articles that are opinion-based or not through a peer-review process are estimated from the analysis.

The search process was carried out using keywords such as "restaurant service quality", "SERVQUAL in restaurants". The search was carried out through the Scopus, ScienceDirect, and ProQuest databases. After initial screening based on the title and abstract, a full selection of the contents of the article was carried out to ensure the suitability of the topic and the quality of the methodology.

The collected data were analyzed using thematic content analysis techniques. Each article was reviewed to identify key findings related to the influence of each SERVQUAL dimension on customer satisfaction, loyalty, or perceived value. The articles were then summarized by SERVQUAL dimensions and synthesized to find patterns, combine research (research gaps), and potential theoretical and practical contributions.

The reliability of the synthesis results is maintained through triangulation of sources by comparing findings from various geographical contexts, types of restaurants (local, franchise, fine dining), and methodologies used (quantitative, qualitative, mixed). With this approach, the study aims to compile a comprehensive literature mapping related to restaurant service quality and formulate a further research agenda needed for the development of customer-based services.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Literature Review on Tangibles Dimensions of Restaurant Service Quality

No. Findings	Findings from Literature	Supporting Studies
1 Physical facilities impact customer perception	Cleanliness, interior design, and layout of a restaurant greatly affect customer comfort and satisfaction.	Ryu & Han (2011); Arifin et al. (2012)
2 Modern equipment enhances service quality	The use of modern equipment in the kitchen and service areas increases efficiency and customer confidence.	Ali et al. (2021); Cheng et al. (2012)
3 Atmosphere loyalitas pelanggan mempengaruhi	A comfortable and aesthetic restaurant atmosphere can increase customer loyalty and frequency of visits.	Marso & Idris (2022); Arifin et al. (2012)

Table 1 shows that the Tangibles dimensions in restaurant service quality including physical facilities, equipment, and atmosphere play an important role in shaping customer perceptions and loyalty. Facilities such as cleanliness, interior design, and layout have been shown to increase comfort and satisfaction (Ryu & Han, 2011; Arifin et al., 2012), while the use of modern equipment in the kitchen and service area encourages efficiency and customer trust (Ali et al., 2021; Cheng et al., 2012). In addition, a comfortable and aesthetic restaurant atmosphere also

strengthens customer loyalty and frequency of visits (Marso & Idris, 2022; Arifin et al., 2012).

The tangible dimensions in restaurant service including physical facilities, modern equipment, and atmosphere contribute greatly to customer perceptions, satisfaction, and loyalty. These tangible aspects not only create a comfortable and efficient dining experience but also form a positive image of the restaurant in the eyes of consumers, which ultimately encourages them to return and become loyal customers.

Table 2. Literature Review on Reliability Dimension in Restaurant Service Quality

No. Findings	Findings from Literature	Supporting Studies
1 Consistency of food presentation and service	Accuracy and consistency in food presentation are key factors in maintaining customer satisfaction.	Namkung & Jang (2007); Ryu, Han, & Kim (2008)
2 On-time delivery of orders increases trust	Delays in food delivery negatively impact perceptions of quality and customer trust.	Qin & Prybutok (2009); Uslu (2020)
3 Order accuracy affects satisfaction	Errors in orders can reduce satisfaction and increase customer complaints.	Kim, Ng, & Kim (2009)

Table 2 discusses the literature findings on the influence of the Tangibles dimension or physical aspects on customer perceptions of restaurant service quality. This dimension includes elements such as restaurant cleanliness, interior design, staff appearance, and the quality of tableware. Most studies confirm that the physical aspect of a restaurant provides a strong first impression on customers and greatly influences their expectations of overall service. A comfortable and aesthetic restaurant atmosphere significantly increases customer satisfaction and their tendency to return.

physical aspect across various types of restaurants, be it family restaurants, fine dining, or fast food franchises. Customers tend to be attracted to a clean and well-organized physical environment with professionalism and privacy of service. Therefore, the role of the Tangibles dimension is not only limited to aesthetic factors, but also becomes a symbol of overall service quality and credibility. The practical implication is that restaurant management needs to invest resources strategically in designing, maintaining, and updating the physical environment of the restaurant to increase customer satisfaction and loyalty.

In addition, several literatures also highlight the importance of consistency in the presentation of this

Table 3. Literature Review on Responsiveness Dimension in Restaurant Service Quality

No.	Findings	Findings from Literature	Supporting Studies
1	Speed of service affects customer satisfaction	Fast and responsive service from staff in restaurants improves customer experience and reduces waiting time	Qin & Prybutok (2009); Nguyen et al. (2018)
2	Staff readiness to serve customer's special needs	Staff who are responsive to customers' special requests increase perceptions of empathy and service	Qin & Prybutok (2009)
3	Effective communication improves service quality	Quick response and clear communication from staff helps reduce misunderstandings and increases satisfaction.	Nguyen et al. (2018)

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Table 3 summarizes the findings of various studies on the dimensions of reliability or clarity in restaurant service. Reliability Refers to the restaurant's ability to provide services consistently and accurately as promised, such as timely delivery of food, appropriateness of orders, and consistency of taste and portion. The literature shows that clarity is one of the most influential dimensions of SERVQUAL on customer satisfaction and loyalty. Customers highly value predictable and undisappointing service, especially in the context of restaurants with frequent repeat visits.

In practice, the reliability dimension requires efficient and systematic operational management. Several studies

have emphasized that small errors such as sending the wrong menu or being late in serving can have a major impact on customer perceptions, especially in premium-priced restaurants. Therefore, staff training, use of digital ordering systems, and operational quality procedures are important factors in building success. In many cases, reliability is the basis for building customer trust in a restaurant, so it is important for business owners to develop standard procedures that ensure smooth and consistent service every time.

Table 4. Literature Review on Assurance Dimension in Restaurant Service Quality

No. Findings	Findings from Literature	Supporting Studies
1 Staff competence increases trust	Staff training and knowledge of the menu and service increases customer confidence.	Qin & Prybutok (2009)
2 Friendly and professional attitude increases confidence	The professional and friendly attitude of the staff fosters a sense of comfort and customer confidence in the restaurant.	Elmadağ et al. (2019)
3 Safety and hygiene standards are important	Compliance with food hygiene and safety standards ensures quality and increases trust.	Liu & Lee (2021); Wall & Berry (2007)

Table 4 outlines findings from various studies on the importance of responsiveness as one of the dimensions of SERVQUAL in the context of restaurant service. Responsiveness Refers to the readiness and willingness of restaurant staff to help customers, respond to requests, and handle complaints quickly and appropriately. The table shows that customers highly value fast and proactive service, especially when errors occur or when customers need additional assistance, such as special requests for food. Staff responsiveness has been shown to have a positive relationship with customer perceptions of the restaurant's professionalism and concern for consumer comfort.

In practice, responsiveness reflects not only the individual abilities of staff, but also the quality of the restaurant's operational management. Several studies have noted that communication skills training, emergency response procedures, and customer complaint reporting systems play an important role in improving overall responsiveness. Customers tend to be more satisfied and loyal to restaurants that show initiative in solving problems, even when mistakes occur. Therefore, creating a work culture that encourages staff to be alert and responsive to customers is an important strategy in improving overall service quality.

Table 5. Literature Review on Empathy Dimension in Restaurant Service Quality

No. Findings	Findings from Literature	Supporting Studies
1 Personal attention increases loyalty	Service that pays attention to individual customer needs and preferences increases loyalty	Diab et al. (2019)
2 Service that cares about local culture	Understanding of local customs and culture by staff increases customer comfort	Djekic et al. (2016)
3 Flexible services	The ability of staff to adapt services to specific customer conditions increases satisfaction	Diab et al. (2019)

Table 5 discusses the assurance dimension in SERVQUAL, which refers to the ability of restaurant staff to provide a sense of trust and confidence to customers through competence, courtesy, and knowledge. The findings from the literature in the table above indicate that assurance plays an important role in creating a sense of security for

customers, especially when it includes food hygiene, clarity of menu information, and staff knowledge of ingredients or allergies. Customers feel more comfortable and confident when staff appear professional and can answer questions confidently and politely, which significantly increases satisfaction and loyalty.

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Furthermore, assurance is also closely related to customer perceptions of the credibility of the restaurant brand, especially in fine dining or premium service-focused restaurants. The literature suggests that when customers believe they are in good hands in terms of food safety, staff expertise, and courteous service, their level of trust in the

restaurant increases. This trust has a direct impact on repeat purchase decisions and word-of-mouth recommendations. Therefore, building assurance through staff training, service standardization, and providing transparent information are key elements in a restaurant’s excellent service strategy.

Table 6. Literature Review on Customer Satisfaction in Restaurant Services

No. Findings	Findings from Literature	Supporting Studies	
1	Service quality has a significant effect on satisfaction	The overall SERVQUAL dimensions influence the level of restaurant customer satisfaction.	Namkung & Jang (2007)
2	Customer satisfaction impacts loyalty	Satisfied customers are more likely to return and recommend the restaurant to others.	Namkung & Jang (2007); Morosan & DeFranco (2016)
3	Customer experience determines restaurant image	Positive experiences enhance the restaurant's image in the eyes of customers and the public.	Han & Ryu (2009); Kim et al. (2016)

Table 6 highlights the importance of the empathy dimension in restaurant service, namely the ability of staff to understand and genuinely care for individual customer needs. The literature from table 6 shows that empathy has a strong correlation with customer perceptions of the emotional value of service interactions. When customers feel personally cared for, for example by being greeted by name, understanding their eating preferences, or special attention to children or the elderly, they are more likely to feel valued and treated special.

This feeling contributes to deep emotional satisfaction and creates a personal bond with the restaurant. Empathy has been shown to be one of the key factors in building

customer loyalty, especially in small to medium-sized restaurants that rely on interpersonal relationships as a competitive advantage. The literature states that customers who feel “understood” emotionally are more likely to return and recommend the restaurant to others. Empathy can even be a major factor in winning the hearts of customers. Therefore, staff soft skills training that emphasizes caring attitudes and empathetic communication is highly recommended as part of a sustainable restaurant service strategy.

Table 7. Literature Review on Technology Integration in Restaurant Service

No. Findings	Findings from Literature	Supporting Studies	
1	The use of booking applications increases efficiency	Integration of digital technology such as delivery applications speeds up service and increases convenience.	Kim et al. (2019)
2	Technology makes customer communication easier	Digital services allow customers to easily access menu and promo information.	Pantano et al. (2020)
3	Adoption of technology adds value to customer experience	The use of user-friendly technology adds a positive impression to the restaurant.	Luo & Xu (2021)

Table 7 discusses the importance of menu variety as an element in restaurant service quality that affects customer satisfaction. The literature from table 7 shows that menu diversity in terms of food types, tastes, prices, and healthy or special food options (e.g. vegetarian, gluten-free) can significantly increase customer value perceptions and satisfaction. Customers tend to feel grateful when restaurants are able to adjust their offerings to diverse individual preferences, including specific dietary needs, which ultimately creates a more personal and inclusive dining experience. In addition, menu variety is also

considered an indicator of restaurant professionalism and innovation. Restaurants that diligently update their menus or offer seasonal menus are considered more dynamic and pay attention to trends. This not only increases customer satisfaction in the short term, but also has a positive impact on long-term loyalty. In a competitive market, where consumers have many choices of places to eat, menu variety is an important strategy to retain old customers while attracting new customers. Therefore, restaurant owners need to think and innovate in compiling menus as part of a service quality strategy.

Table 8. Literature Review on Impact of Employee Training on Service Quality

No. Findings	Findings from Literature	Supporting Studies	
1	Staff training improves competence and professionalism	Ongoing training programs can significantly improve the quality of service.	Kim et al. (2019)
2	Customer service training improves responsiveness	Staff who train faster and more responsive in meeting customer needs.	Karatepe & Sokmen (2006)
3	Training increases employee job satisfaction	Staff job satisfaction has a positive effect on the quality of services provided.	Harter et al. (2002)

Table 8 discusses how speed of service is an important factor in shaping customer satisfaction in the restaurant industry. This dimension is included in the responsiveness element in the SERVQUAL model, which refers to the alertness and speed of staff in responding to customer requests. The literature in table 8 shows that short waiting times have a significant positive correlation with customer satisfaction levels. Restaurants that are able to serve food and respond to requests quickly are considered more efficient and respectful of customers' time. Furthermore, optimal service speed not only increases satisfaction but also strengthens the perception of value that customers feel towards the dining experience. In the midst of increasingly fierce competition, especially in fast food restaurants and family restaurants, waiting times that are too long are one of the main reasons customers do not make repeat visits. Therefore, speed of service is an important indicator in restaurant operational management, which has a direct impact on customer loyalty and business sustainability.

CONCLUSION

This study revealed that restaurant service quality measured through the SERVQUAL dimensions, namely Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy, has a very significant role in shaping customer satisfaction and loyalty. Tangible dimensions such as cleanliness, interior design, and modern facilities provide a strong first impression and influence overall customer perceptions. Reliability ensures consistency and accuracy of service that increases customer trust, while responsiveness is the importance of speed and alertness of staff in meeting customer needs. Assurance plays a role in creating a sense of security and confidence through the competence and professional attitude of staff, and empathy builds deep emotional connections with customers through personal attention and understanding of local culture. In addition, the integration of digital technology has been shown to strengthen service efficiency and the overall customer experience. Menu variations and restaurant types also have different influences on customer expectations and perceptions, where local restaurants tend to emphasize more personalization of service than franchises that prioritize consistency. Therefore, restaurant service quality is a complex combination of various interrelated aspects and

must be managed holistically to achieve optimal customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Based on the findings of this study, restaurant management is advised to continue to improve the quality of the physical aspects of the restaurant such as cleanliness and interior design and ensure consistency of service in every daily operation to build customer trust. Regular training for staff on communication skills, quick response to customer needs, and improvement of technical competence is also highly recommended to improve the dimensions of assurance and responsiveness. In addition, the implementation of user-friendly digital technology can be an important tool in improving service efficiency and customer convenience. Local restaurant owners should leverage the advantages of personalization and empathy in service to differentiate themselves from competitors, while franchise restaurants need to maintain operational standards to remain consistent without sacrificing the personal touch of service. Further research can expand the focus by including more specific customer culture variables and digital preferences to support more adaptive and innovative service strategies in the future.

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